

WAYS TO IMPROVE KNOWLEDGE IN LANGUAGE LEARNING .

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Abstract: *Are you a morning or afternoon person? If you can work out when your brain is at its sharpest then you should cram in your language learning at this time. Some people work best first thing in the morning and switch off after lunchtime, while for others it takes a while to get going every day.*

Key words: *Knowing ,learn, vocabulary, listen ,better.*

Learning a language is more than sitting in a classroom and trying to absorb all the information from the teacher. It also requires extra effort of you. Doing some additional work is important if you really want to boost your language skills. I've been studying English for ten years now, and here are some of the things I do that have helped me a lot. Have a look at these ten ways to boost your English language skills and perhaps they can help you too. We are all different and it is the differences that make the world so diverse and complete. Since every individual is unique, the way each person learns is also unique. We all have different learning styles and it is important that you know which one is yours. Knowing the way you learn best will make you understand yourself better and enjoy your learning experiences. This is the first step towards boosting your language skills. We are all different and it is the differences that make the world so diverse and complete. Since every individual is unique, the way each person learns is also unique. We all have different learning styles and it is important that you know which one is yours. Knowing the way you learn best will make you understand yourself better and enjoy your learning experiences. This is the first step towards boosting your language skills. Many teachers recognize that having a high level of English can help them hugely in advancing their careers and bring them more opportunities. In fact, it is now estimated that a third of the world's population (around 2 billion people) are able to speak English¹. And as a result, it has become more important than ever to know the Ways to Quickly Improve Your English Language Skills. Watch movies in English.

...Immerse yourself in English language news. ...Start a vocabulary book of useful words. ...Have conversations in English. Practice, practice, practice. ...Curiosity doesn't always kill the cat. ...Don't forget to have fun while you learn. The extent to which you can write down your daily thoughts and ideas and what happens to you in another language is a great indicator of how fluent you are. Writing in a journal not only tells you how well you can express yourself, but also the extent of your vocabulary and second language knowledge. If you notice that you do not have enough vocabulary to express an idea, that's when the learning starts. Use dictionaries and Google to help you with that. The more you search for new words and expressions, the more your vocabulary will expand. Write everyday, if you can, even if it is just a sentence or a paragraph; but make sure you write! Also, the more you write about different subjects, the better. If you are a visual learner, and can only remember things best when you write them, I think a personalized dictionary could work very well for you. Have a separate notepad with you and write down the unknown words you come across. Under each word, jot down its meaning, as well as a sentence created by you showing that you know how to use it accurately. If you have a native friend to take a look at it and check that it is all right, that would be perfect. For me, listening to a second language can give me almost the same benefit as reading it. They all help you to expand your vocabulary, enhance your knowledge of grammar, speak properly and so forth. But there is a slight difference between them; Listening will show you, loud and clear, how the words are pronounced. This is the key to making yourself understood when you speak. Listening to a variety of things is also important for boosting your English language skills. News, radio, movies, songs, cooking programmes sports... They will all help you to this question. When we learn our native language, first we listen, then we speak, then we read and finally we write. Listening, speaking, reading and writing are the four language skills we need to develop for complete communication. Listening and reading are receptive: input, i.e. the exposure you have to authentic language in use. Speaking and writing are productive: output, i.e. the action of producing language as part of the process of second language learning. To achieve these four basic

language skills, you need to surround yourself with English: make English part of your life at home, at work, during your free time. Read on to find tips that will help you overcome the difficulties you might be experiencing to improve your English skills. Expose yourself to the language as much as possible: practice makes perfect, which means that if you want to improve a certain skill you have to practice it. As a beginner learner you will need to achieve all 4 language skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing.

Listening: It plays a very important part in learning any language. Effective listening ensures understanding and it helps improve accuracy when speaking, among other things. How can you improve your listening skills? By listening actively, i.e. paying attention not only on what is said, but also how it is said. So, listen:

1. To music –old or modern; the type you prefer, but pay attention to the lyrics. (sometimes reading the lyrics may help you understand the song).
2. To movies, TV shows, news, entertainments, the radio – try the classics. If you can watch DVD's you can watch the movie several times. Watching with subtitles and then, when you feel more comfortable, without them. You can have English radio at home or on your mobile phone. Even if are not actually listening to it, your ears will be getting used to the sounds of the language.
3. Attend plays, exhibitions, talks, etc. in English organized by English speaking schools or communities

Speaking: It is often the hardest of the four language skills, but as soon as you can speak a little English there are lots of ways to improve quickly and have tons of fun.

4. Join voiced chats. Technology has advanced a lot in terms of social networks so, wherever you live, you'll find a chat-room to join.
5. Talk and record yourself. This may sound funny, but it will help you realize how you can improve by repeating the recording several times till you feel happy with the results.
6. Talk to your classmates in English when you are not in class. You can even make a group to play games, have a meal or just chat together.

Reading: It is a process of the brain and it takes time to develop: your mind has to attach meaning to the words, phrases and expressions represented by symbols, plus get to understand the grammar and structure of the language used in the passage to read. If you develop strong reading skills, it'll be very helpful to your future. You can read:

7. Books in English and

articles on the web. Maybe, books you have already read in your mother tongue or which have been turned into movies. Try to start with easy books, even children's books and comics: The images will help you understand even if you don't know all the words 8. Switch the operating system of your mobile phone, your PC or tablet into English. Associating a function with a certain word, will improve your vocabulary. Writing: Even though it may be intimidating to a lot of people, anyone can get used to writing with a little discipline and a willingness to learn. 9. Write down words or expressions you think useful with their meaning and examples. If you see them in sentences you will remember them better. You can use them if you keep a diary. 10. Write comments in English blogs. At present blogs are websites that resemble journals. Lots of people use them to expose their ideas on a certain topic or to explain things – from how to knit a scarf, to very complicated ones where technical or philosophical topics are dealt with

Conclusion Learning English doesn't always have to mean sitting in the classroom and studying tricky grammar. In fact, English language teachers encourage you to do plenty of extra learning outside of school. There are a number of ways to improve your understanding of the language, many of which can actually be a lot of fun. It's also a well-known fact that different people respond to different learning methods. Sometimes simply sitting in the classroom or reading a course book is not right for you. It can be beneficial to do some additional work. So if you're keen to improve your English (or any other second language for that matter) then consider some of these handy tips to get you on your way. Not everything will work for you but, if you add a few of these ideas to your day-to-day language learning, you'll certainly see some improvement.

References

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